

THE ROLE OF PAREMIOLOGY IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract.

The article highlights the history of the study of paremiological units in Russian linguistics, the analysis of scientific research of paremias as special linguistic units demonstrates the different positions of linguists.

Keywords.

Paremia, paremiology, phraseology, linguistic status, aphorism, metaphor, epithet, comparison.

Introduction

Paremiology, as a part of linguistics, cannot yet be considered a well-established discipline of scientific knowledge. At the moment, we can only discuss some fundamental concepts, such as paremia, a paremiological unit, but there is no generally accepted systematisation of paremiological material in paremiology, its volume and boundaries have not been determined, and the subject of paremiology itself remains ambiguous.

Paremiology is a subset of phraseology, which is a branch of philology dedicated to the study and classification of proverbs, proverbs, antipreferences, proverbs, sayings, vellerisms, mottos, slogans, aphorisms, riddles, omens, and other sayings whose main purpose is a brief figurative verbal expression of traditional values and attitudes based on a group, nation, etc.

Paremies are specific units and linguistic signals that are vital components of human communication. These symbols communicate particular information, designate common life and mental conditions, or indicate relationships between those and other items.

All of the world's parables transmit the same basic circumstances and have comparable logical meaning, changing only in the visuals used to convey the logical content.

Despite having the same ancient Greek root, the Russian terms "paremy" and "parimy" denote distinct things.

Paremiology is closely connected to paremiography, which is involved with the collecting, storage, and processing of materials for paremiologists' study.

Comparative emiology is the study of paremy in various languages and cultures.

Grigory Lvovich Permyakov (1919-1983) and Sergei Danilovich Mastepanov were prominent Russian paremiologists.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

According to V.M. Mokienko, the paremiological surge in linguistics that phraseologists prophesied 30 years ago has exceeded all predictions. Modern society's dynamization has resulted in the activation of national consciousness, as well as interest in such a minor category of folklore as proverbs and sayings. Liberation from censorship, freedom of speech, demand for advertising, and open access of any "wit" to the Internet space and the media provided proverbs with such a powerful functioning that such passionaries of European paremiology as Erasmus of Rotterdam could not even dream of in the Renaissance or the formation of nations. Could not have imagined, but it was they who provided the material groundwork for paremiology as a folkloristic and ethnographic science, allowing us, linguists, to eventually engage not only in the examination of their conceptual underpinning, but also of their simply linguistic character, several centuries later.

Long before the word "paremiology," there was interest in the study and systematisation of figurative-prophetic sayings as a sort of expressive means of the Russian language. Proverbs and sayings, the most striking expressive methods, had already piqued the interest of scientists as genres of oral folklore. Since the XVII century, their hand-written collections have been known. The first printed collection, "Collection of 4,291 Russian historic proverbs," was produced by A.A. Barsov, a well-known professor at Moscow University.

"Russian Folk Proverbs and Proverbs," the next comprehensive collection, was prepared by I. M. Snegirev.

The major work of V. I. Dahl "Proverbs of the Russian People" completes this effort on the collecting and dissemination of proverbs and sayings. The collection "Winged words" («рлате слова») by S. V. Maksimov is larger in scope, since it includes numerous folk sayings and phrases that are not proverbs and proverbs. He discusses the origins of specific figurative terms (undernote, gibberish) (одноотна, алимат), phraseological units (to pull a gimp, to gag a belt) (тнут канител, аткнут а ос), proverbs and sayings.

In M. I. Mikhelson's compilation ""Walking and Appropriate Words" and "Russian Thought and Speech. Strange and unique. "Russian Phraseology Experience" and "Collection of Figurative Words and Allegories" "S.V. Maximov treats phraseology extensively. It encompasses all metaphorical identifiers of occurrences.

According to N.F. Alefirenko, assigning paremy to the basic phraseological resource of the language is a contentious issue since paremy mixes characteristics with sentence attributes and free combinations. "The term "paremy" is considered by most current academics as aphorisms of folk provenance, especially proverbs and sayings" .

A proverb is a unit of study in linguistics, folklore, psychology, and ethnography. In the "Dictionary of the Russian Language," S.I. Ozhegov defines proverb and proverb: "Proverb is a brief folk saying having an educational connotation." A proverb is a metaphorical term that, unlike a proverb, does not constitute a whole sentence. "

The problem of defining the linguistic status of proverbs remains significant in linguistics. Some experts classify them as part of phraseology, while others distinguish proverbs from phraseological terms.

Proverbs are not considered phraseology by most phraseologists since they do not enter into speech in conjunction with other linguistic elements inside sentences.

The presence of an environment for a phraseological unit is highlighted as a key aspect. The challenge of differentiating proverbs and phraseological units is exacerbated further by the fact that the most significant aspect of determining the linguistic status of proverbs is to characterise the qualities of stable units. In addition to proverbs, there is a form of stable turn in the language known as a proverb. "Proverbs are a poetic form of words: metaphor, comparison, epithet, definition," a part of an opinion, according to M. A. Rybnikova, a well-known researcher and collector of paremics, whereas "a proverb is a whole notion, a complete thinking."

Until now, the words proverb and proverb have been used interchangeably in folk speech, among authors and journalists, and among local speakers who are unfamiliar with the terminological intricacies of paremiology. Another example is the use of proverbs and sayings as folklore, ethnographic, and linguistic terminology. For a long period, there was a necessity in European paremiology to rigorously separate them. These concepts gradually began to diverge fairly clearly in Russian and other philological and folkloristic traditions. V. I. Dal clearly and lapidarily defined this distinction, which was already established in his day.

A proverb, in his opinion, is a "short parable," a judgement, a sentence, or a lesson expressed in plain language and circulated under the coinage of a nationality, "the proverb is" a devious expression, figurative speech, a simple allegory, a bluntness, a way of expression, but without a parable, judgement, or conclusion... this is one first half of the proverb".

As a result, the latter contains popular sayings like as You can't simply pull a fish out of a pond; do you enjoy riding and hauling sledges? To the proverbs - to dump from a painful head to a healthy one, to rake in the heat with someone else's hands, that is, such units that many linguists today term phraseological units.

Of course, not all scientists and proverbs and sayings collectors still use these terms in the old sense.

In his "Dictionary of Russian Proverbs and Sayings," one of the most notable linguists and lexicographers, V.P. Zhukov, presents a particularly unique interpretation of them. By proverbs, he means short folk sayings of a full grammatical type, with both a direct and metaphorical plan, and by sayings, he means solely literal sayings. The former include phrases such as: Whatever the youngster is enjoying himself, as long as he does not cry, while the later contain phrases such as: Money is a matter of gain, or Spit is a girl's attractiveness. Some current Russian paremiologists-linguists recognise this unusual difference between proverbs and sayings, whereas the majority adhere to a long-accepted terminological tradition.

V.P. Zhukov's terminological innovation is unwarranted in our opinion, because the ugly proverbs he labels sayings preserve all of the fundamental elements of paremias with a complete syntactic structure. So, while it will always be useful in studies such as Study; Labor feeds, but idleness ruins; Learning is better than money, and the image is missing; their aphorism, rhythm, and semantic capacity make them proverbs, completely suitable metaphorical - like Learning, the root is bitter, but the fruit is pleasant; You can't get a fish out of a pond without work. Learning is light, and ignorance is darkness.

The distinction between proverbs and sayings is seen in this way by the European tradition.

English terminology. idiom and proverb, fr. proverbe and dicton, it. Sprichwort and Redensart, for example.

Linguists and paremiologists have previously done a lot to define the status of paremias, separate them and find functional potencies, analyse their syntactic, lexical, stylistic, and sociolinguistic features, genre specialities, and so on.

The status of various forms of paremias, as well as their terminological and categorization interpretation, are and will continue to be debated. Any paremiological theory, it appears, should be confirmed by the algebra of practise, that is, by creating dictionaries.

CONCLUSION

The investigation of scientific research of proverbs as distinctive linguistic units reveals many academic perspectives. According to N.F. Alefirenko, aphorisms of folk provenance, particularly proverbs and proverbs, are paremy. Paremys, like other stable units of language, are classified into thematic fields based on linguistic and extralinguistic elements and the construction of a paremiological view of the world.

Each scholar has his or her own arguments for and against incorporating paremys in the phraseological fund. Due to the various and different viewpoints on their assignment to phraseology or separation from phraseology in Russian, the examination of paremiology is not easy.

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